

India's Little France

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ABSTRACT

Pondicherry, formally known as Puduchery, and normally alluded to as Pondy. Pondy is one of the seven Association Rons of India which is limited by the southern territory of Tamil Nadu. This previous French state is an ideal combination of the customary Indian sensibilities and French engineering, making it a fantastic break that offers the smartest possible scenario. The Streets of the French Quarter of Pondicherry, otherwise called White Town, are specked with beguiling mustard-yellow frontier structures with bougainvillea loaded walls. These are mixed with comfortable bistros and stylish stores that offer luscious French cooking and drinks. Essentially walking around these roads, can give the voyager an understanding into the fantasy appeal of Pondicherry. The uniqueness of Pondicherry town invariably lies in skillful town planning and Franco Tamil architecture. The town is built on the model of bastide, a fortified French coastal town of the late 18th Century. All the regions of Puduchery were under the French rule for 138 years. On November 1, 1954, the French possessions in India were de facto transferred to the Indian Union and became a Union Territory. But only in 1963, Puducherry became officially an integral part of India. In addition to the historical sites, Puducherry is home to the French Consulate, a number of cultural institutions, and the Foyer du Soldat for French Army veterans of war. The French Institute, the Alliance Francais, and the Ecole Francais d'Extrême Orient stand out among the cultural institutions. In these articles explain the details of french culture development in India.

Keywords : French, India, Region, Culture, Alliancce.

Introduction

Pondicherry, officially known as Pondicherry City, is the capital and the most populous city of the Indian Union Territory of Puducherry. The city is located in the Pondicherry district on the southeast coast of India, and is surrounded by the state of Tamil Nadu.¹ The city of Puducherry is the Capital of this Union Territory. It lies on the east coast about 162 kms south of Chennai (Madras) located on the Coromandel Coast of the Bay of Bengal.²

Historical Background

In 1674 the French East India Company set up a trading centre at Pondicherry and this outpost eventually became the chief French settlement in India. Five trading posts were established along the south Indian coast between 1668 and 1674. The city was separated by a canal into the French Quarter and the Indian Quarter.³

During the Anglo-French wars (1742-1763), Puducherry changed hands frequently. On 16 January 1761, the British captured Pondicherry from the French, but it was returned under the Treaty of Paris (1763) at the conclusion of the Seven Years' War. In 1792, Venant of Durfort, son of the Count of Civrac, was made governor of Pondicherry, thanks to his uncle Emmanuel-Félicité, Duke of Duras, who had been made president of the Compagnie des Indes in 1788. After an outstanding military career in Europe, Venant fought hard to destroy all revolutionary hopes in Pondicherry, as republican ideals coming from France were threatening the economic stability of the region. He took great care to maintain commercial relations with other European powers in the region. His links with England were strengthened through his marriage with Catherine Browne of Kilmor. Venant died in July 1792 and was buried at Our Lady of Angels in Pondicherry. The British took control of the area again in 1793 at the Siege of Pondicherry amid the Wars of the French Revolution, and returned it to France in 1814. When the British gained control of India in the late 1850s, they allowed the French to retain their settlements in the country. Pondicherry, Mahdicherry, Mah, Yanam, Karaikal and Chandernagor remained a part of French India until 1954 when it was incorporated into the Indian Union with the rest of French India.⁴

French colonies

For a span of two hundred years, the French people ruled in Pondicherry. The French rule came to an end in the year 1954 in Pondicherry. It is there lifestyle, occupation, cultures, tradition that made Pondicherry a beautiful spot with a touch of French culture in it. Also called as French quarter of Pondicherry, the old buildings and houses were built by the French people during their reign.

French colony Pondicherry is one of the main attractions of Pondicherry Tourism. The colony is filled with old houses of the French period. The old houses were so well built and well maintained that they still have the power to attract tourists from the corners of the world.. It is a neat and clean colony. we can feel the difference between the style, culture of French and Indian people just by taking a stroll in the colony.⁵

They are now heritage sites of Pondicherry. The colony is laid in a grid pattern with parallel roads cutting across each other at a ninety-degree angle. It is built in the exact way French people live in their country. The houses are mostly painted in Blue and yellow color with white as the highlighting color. The colors look vibrant on the French style buildings and high compound walls. This French colony of India is a fusion of French architectural beauty and tropical climate beauty. Top tourist attractions of Pondicherry are.,

French Street

The wide streets lined with trees that run through the Colony are named on French streets the name starts with 'rue' (a French word which means street in English). The Rue Romain Rolland Street, Rue de la marineruns by the French colony. French colony brings forward the vintage vibes and aesthetic finish in old French-style buildings. The beauty of French culture and tradition will make you feel you are in a different country altogether. French colony is definitely one of the best Places t in Pondicherry.

The White Town

This area was reserved for Whites when French rule dominated in this region of the Indian subcontinent. While exploring this region, you will spot arched gates adorned with bougainvillea, white and yellow walls and clean European-style streets. This picturesque locale transports you back in time. The stunning architecture makes this place quite a visual delight.⁶

The Botanical Garden

The Botanical Garden is located to the south of the New Bus Stand. An aquarium and a botanical garden were established in this town of French Colony Pondicherry in 1826. It is spread over 22 acres and is a famous retreat for the tourists and the locals. Perrotet was responsible for designing this botanical garden and hence his memorial can be found on the premises. He introduced several exotic plants from all over the world in this garden. There are about twenty-eight plots in this garden and each one has a separate theme.

Statue of Dupleix

Dupleix left Puducherry in 1754, French recognition of his contribution came only in 1870, with the commissioning of two statues—one in Puducherry and the other in France. It is now situated in Goubert Avenue at the end of Rock Beach. It was first installed on 16 July 1870. In 1979 the statue was moved from its previous location in the middle of the current Bharathy park to the current location at the beach. Restoration of the Dupleix statue was undertaken by the Public Works Department (PWD) of the government of Puducherry in 2014.⁷

Arikamedu

Arikamedu is an archaeological site in Southern India, in Kakkayanthope, Ariyankuppam Commune, Puducherry. It is 4 kilometres (2.5 mi) from the capital, Pondicherry of the Indian territory of Puducherry. Sir Mortimer Wheeler 1945, and Jean-Marie Casal conducted archaeological excavations there in 1947–1950. The site was identified as the port of Podouke, known as an "emporium" in the Periplus of the Erythraean Sea and Ptolemy. Digs have found Amphorae, Arretine ware, Roman lamps, glassware, glass and stone beads, and gems at the site.

Based on these excavations, Wheeler concluded that the Arikamedu was a Greek (Yavana) trading post that traded with Rome, starting during the reign of Augustus Caesar, and lasted about two hundred years—from the late first century BCE to the first and second centuries CE. Subsequent investigation by Vimala Begley from 1989 to 1992 modified this assessment, and now place the period of settlement from the 2nd century BCE to the 8th century CE.

Significant findings at Arikamedu include numerous Indo-Pacific beads, which facilitated fixing the period of its origin. Red and black ceramics, known as megalithic stones or Pandukal in Tamil meaning "old stones" and used to mark graves, have existed at the site even prior to dates of the trading post, and also in later periods.⁸

Basilica of the Sacred Heart of Jesus

Its situated on the south boulevard in Pondicherry, India. its an oriental specimen of Gothic architecture. It contains rare stained glass panels depicting events from the life of Christ and saints of the Catholic Church. In recent years it has become one of the famous pilgrimage spots for Christians.

In the year 1895, the then Archbishop Mgr.Gandy consecrated the Archdiocese of Pondicherry to the Sacred Heart of Jesus. He wished to build a new church in devotion of Sacred Heart of Jesus. Rev. Fr. Telesphore Welter, the parish priest of Nellithope prepared the building plan and parish priest of Cathedral Rev. Fr. Fourcaud commenced the construction of the new church in 1902 at the Southern side of Pondicherry.

Our Lady of Angels Church

Our Lady of Angels Church is the fourth oldest church in Puducherry, a Union territory in South India. The original structure was built in Greco Roman architecture by Napoleon III in 1855, with the architect being Louis Guerre. It is the only church that offers mass in three languages namely French, Tamil and English.

It is believed to be based on Notre-Dame in Paris and the Basilica at Lourdes. Napoleon III visited the chapel as the first place when he visited Pondicherry. It is understood that there were

four churches in the campus and British demolished the church and converted it into two orphanages. It is believed that Napoleon III donated an oil painting of Our Lady of Assumption to the church.⁹

Joan of Arc

Joan of Arc otherwise "The Maid of Orleans", is considered a heroine of France and a Roman Catholic saint. She was born to a peasant family at Domremy in north-east France. Joan said she received visions of the Archangel Michael, Saint Margaret and Saint Catherine instructing her to support Charles VII and recover France from English domination late in the Hundred Years War.

Twenty-five years after her execution, an inquisitorial court authorized by Pope Callixtus III examined the trial, pronounced her innocent, and declared her a martyr. Joan of Arc was beatified in 1909 and canonized in 1920. She is one of the nine secondary patron saints of France. Due to the French influence in Puducherry this life-size statue in white marble, a gift by Francois Gaudart, was erected in 1923 in the middle of a garden and facing the Church of Our Lady of Angels.¹⁰

French War Memorial

The monument was erected in 1937 and inaugurated on 3 April 1938 by governor Crocicchia. A subsidy of 5,000 rupees was entered into the colonial budget and was granted "to the committee designated by the decree of 14 January 1936, for the erection of a monument to the memory of the inhabitants of French India who died for France during the 1914-1918 war." It was designed by the sculptor Gaston Petit and an architect named Delafon.

A bronze plaque lists the names of soldiers who died during the First World War. Further plaques were added, listing the names of soldiers who died during World War Two, the French War in Indochina and the Algerian War. The monument remains the property of France. The memorial is decorated and illuminated yearly on Bastille Day (14 July) in honour of the soldiers

from the colony who took part in World War One. French government officials visit the memorial on occasion and lay flowers at the foot of the monument.¹¹

Old Lighthouse

A lighthouse was constructed in Pondicherry in the nineteenth century by the French rulers. The project was finally taken up during the tenure of Governor Saint Simon in 1835. Louis Guerre was the engineer of the project. The foundation stone for the lighthouse was laid at the end of 1835 and the inauguration ceremony took place in February 1836.

The height of the lighthouse is 29 meters. It has a round tower and a square base. The cost of construction was 10,000 francs. The foundation has a depth of nine meters. Its light beam could be seen from a distance of 15 miles. The light source consisted of six oil lamps and two reflectors. The light source was converted to electric lamps in 1913. The power of the lamp was increased in 1931. The new lamp had a range of 26 nautical miles. It took 36 seconds for one full rotation of the beam. The new lighthouse started functioning in 1979.¹²

Aayi Mandapam

Aayi Mandapam is a heritage monument in Pondicherry, India built during the time of Napoleon III, Emperor of France. It is situated in center of Bharathi park. The monument commemorates the provision of water to the French city during his reign. It was named after a lady courtesan called Ayi. The Governor of Pondicherry sent a letter to the French king thanking him for sending the architect, Mon. Lamairesse. The King told him to thank Aayi and wrote that she deserved a monument. Aayi's monument is still present in Pondicherry. It is flanked by important buildings like the French consulate, the secretariat and the Governor's bhavan. A stone plaque written in traditional Tamil and Latin pays tribute to Aayi's deed and thanks her for providing water for the people of the town.¹³

Khuthbapalli

Khuthbapalli is an 18th-century mosque of Pondicherry. Khuthbapalli is believed to be the first mosque built in Pondicherry, though not at its present location but in the White Town of

Pondicherry. According to the Dutch map of Pondicherry Fort in 1693, two mosques are located in the White Town of Pondicherry. Meerapalli was relocated during the first half of the 18th Century to the present location as Khuthbapalli, till the destruction of the White Town of Pondicherry by the English in 1761.

This was the ancient mosque that the French soldiers of Dupleix came to destroy in 1761 but were stopped in the process due to the Muslims of Pondicherry and especially by the timely intervention of Abdul Rahman. The French renamed the rue de la monnaie to rue Victor Simonel which stands same to this day. Actually rue de la monnaie was known as rue de la mosquee in Pondicherry during the Governorship of Joseph François Dupleix. Rue de la mosquee means Mosque Street in English meaning that the street housed the ancient mosque of Khuthbapalli.

Mirapalli

Its is the oldest standing mosque of Pondicherry. It was constructed during the first quarter of the 18th century. The renowned Arab Navigator Sulaiman Al Mahri mentions the Port of Bandikeri during the later part of 15th century or the first part of 16th century along the coromandel coast which is identified as Pondicherry in later days. A Muslim settlement was already there. The mosque was originally built along the lines of the Indo-Islamic architecture. The Old structure has survived around which new extensions have been constructed.¹⁴

Vedapureeswarar Temple

Vedapureeswarar Temple in Puducherry, in the South Indian union territory of Puducherry, is dedicated to the Hindu god Shiva. Constructed in the Dravidian style of architecture, the temple was demolished by the French troops in 1748. Shiva is worshipped as Vedapureeswarar and his consort Parvathi as Tiripurasundari. A granite wall surrounds the temple, enclosing all its shrines. The temple has a five-tiered rajagopuram, the gateway tower. A Dewan named Dewan Kandappa Mudaliar expanded the temple with the help of public contributions in 1788.¹⁵

Conclusion

Pondicherry is a residue of colonial past that France left in India. This place has an aesthetic advantage of coromandal coast of Bay of Bengal. The beaches, colonial buildings, resorts, monuments and others make this place a good getaway spot. Pondicherry is a famous tourist destination in India. The monuments of gothic era, museums, religious spots and others make this place a unique destination in South India. The festivals and culture of the land also keeps it apart from other destinations in India. The points of attraction that make this place a must in Pondicherry tour package are French consulate, French Institute, French schools, French buildings, Monuments, churches and many more. A local guide accompanies the tourist who is fluent in both English and French. These attractions make Pondicherry isa India's Little France.

References

¹Directorate of Information Technology, *Pondicherry Municipality*, Pondicherry.

² National Informatics Centre, *Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology*, Government of India.

³ S. P. SEN, *The French in India (1765–1816)*, Calcutta 1958, p. 439.

⁴ Dr. Sarala Gopalan, *A Situational Analysis Of Women And Girls In Pondicherry*, National Commission For Women New Delhi, 2005, pp.2-3.

⁵M.P. Sridharan,*Papers on French Colonial Rule in India*,Calicut,1997,pp.2-4.

⁶P.A Sampathkumar and Andre Carof mep, *History of Pondicherry Mission: An Outline*, Chennai, 1999,p.5.

⁷ INTACH Pondicherry (2004), *Architectural Heritage of Pondicherry*, 1st ed. Puducherry.

⁸ Wheeler, R.E.M., Ghosh A., and Deva K., “*Arikamedu: an Indo – Roman Trading Station on the East Coast of India*”, *Ancient India*, vol. 2, p. 17–125, 1946.

⁹ P. Raja & Rita Nath Keshari, *Glimpses of Pondicherry*, Pondicherry, 2005.